

Green hydrogen production with offshore wind at Colombian Caribbean Sea: Analysis for Atlántico Department's coast

Students: Bermejo, Edwin;
Berrío, Julián; Llain, Jose;
Rincón, Andrés.

Professors: Schlipf, David;
Zambrano, Habib.

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The background features a series of concentric circles in shades of light blue and white, creating a ripple effect. A white, wavy line curves across the right side of the image, overlapping the circles.

Introduction

[1]

NUEVA DEMANDA DE H₂ Y DERIVADOS DE BAJAS EMISIONES

[1]

Technology state - Electrolyzers

Technology	Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOE)	Alkaline Electrolysis (AEL)	Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (PEMEL)
Main characteristic	High-temperature (~ 700 °C) electrolysis technology.	Use a liquid electrolyte.	It has the highest TRL (7-8) when it comes to coupling with a dynamic electric input. [2]
Highest efficiency up to 2019	≥ 79 %	~ 70 %	~ 60 %
Advantages	High efficiency.	Cost-effective solution.	Shorter start-up times.
Challenges for offshore applications	High temperatures challenge material stability. Leakage could increase, thus probable fire event.	Liquid electrolyte increase the likelihood of leakage and maintenance requirements.	Use expensive catalysts (e.g. platinum/iridium).

Technology state – Offshore Wind Platforms

Floating Platforms

[2]

Fixed Foundations

Monopile

Tripile

Tripod

Jacket

Hexabase

Gravity foundation

[3]

Energy Transmission Vectors

Energy transmission vectors

Electric power transmission

Offshore hydrogen pipelines

High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC)

High Voltage Alternating Current (HVAC)

Static pipelines

Flexible pipelines and risers

- 1) Stainless steel carcass
- 2) Polymer fluid barrier
- 3) Carbon steel press
- 4) Anti-wear / binder
- 5) Carbon steel
- 6) Polymer

Wind Farm Location Selection

Water Depth

Offshore Wind Technical Potential

Ship Density

Fishing Activity Usage

Environmental Areas

Initial Offshore Exploration Areas

Wind Farm Location

[5]

Requirements

Studies and approvals

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Structures

Turbines

Energy Storage

Substations

Wiring

Hydrogen

Alkaline Electrolyzer

Reverse osmosis desalinators

Hydrogen Storage

Transportation

Business model

Marketing

Others

Safety Protocols

Typology selection

Typologies

1. Centralised onshore electrolysis

2. Decentralised offshore electrolysis

3. Centralised offshore electrolysis

Centralized onshore electrolysis

Fig. Onshore electrolysis system typology layout using spar platform, dynamic electric cabling, and both an offshore and onshore substation

Advantages

- Easier installation and lower cost of electrolysis onshore.
- Electrolysis technology does not need further validation for offshore conditions.

Disadvantages

- Submarine wiring costs higher than pipelines in large farms at longer distances from shore
- High cost of High voltage converters

Technical Parameters Estimation

Wind potential methodology

Hydrogen production necessary

- A demand of 790kt of H₂ with low emission derivatives is estimated for Colombia in 2040 [1]. The objective is to cover the current demand (150kTon [1]) which represents 19% of the demand in 2040.

Energy required for Electrolyzer

- $E_{total,electrolyzer} = H_2production \cdot E_{Electrolyzer/kgH_2}$
- $E_{Electrolyzer/kgH_2} = \frac{47,6kWh}{kgH_2}, Efficiency = 0,7$

Annual energy production

- $AEP = P_{turbine} \cdot 8760 \cdot capacityfactor$
- $capacityfactor = 0,5$

Number of turbine required

- 117 Wind turbine (Vestas V236 15.00MW)

Wind speed during the year at 100m [5]

With a code in MATLAB, we calculate the annual Wind speed at hub heigh (150m) → 9,03m/s

ANNUAL ENERGY PRODUCTION

Vesta V236-15,00MW

- Mean power of Turbine during the year is 8MW
- Capacity factor=0,53

Wind farm effects

[Video by Siemens Gamesa]

- The turbine reduces wind speed in downwind areas.
- The relative location of the wind and rotor causes the wake to change its orientation relative to the turbine frame.
- This affects the total resulting power of the wind farm

Wind farm effects

- The use of coordinate relative for de calculates of wind farm effects

Wind farm effects

Economical Assessment

Economical Assessment

Item	Quantity	Unit cost	Total cost	Unit	Periodicity	Reference
Turbine Vestas V236 15 MW	117	\$ 13,2	\$ 1.544,4	MUSD	Initial investment	<u>Vestas V236-15.0</u>
Turbine maintenance	1	\$ 48,0	\$ 5,6	MUSD/year	Annual	<u>Wind Turbine Cost</u>
Wiring	1762	\$ 0,2	\$ 325,3	MUSD	Initial investment	<u>Vestas-v236-15-0</u>
Wiring installation	1762	\$ 0,0	\$ 54,2	MUSD	Initial investment	<u>Vestas-v236-15-0</u>
Electrolyzers	11	\$ 48,0	\$ 527,5	MUSD	Initial investment	<u>Water electrolysis systems</u>
Licenses			\$ 1,0	MUSD	Initial investment	
Turbine foundation	117	\$ 3,0	\$ 351,0	MUSD	Initial investment	<u>Vestas-v236-15-0</u>
Land purchase	250088	\$ 133,3	\$ 33,3	MUSD	Initial investment	
Others Initial Investments			\$ 851,0	MUSD	Initial investment	

Summary

Initial investment	\$ 3.687,7	MUSD
Hydrogen anual sales	\$ 300,0	MUSD
Operative costs	\$ 6,6	MUSD

Economical Assessment

■ Cash Flow...

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Conclusion and future works

Green hydrogen has been identified as a sustainable and profitable way to produce energy. A renewable source such as wind energy is ideal to move hydrogen production, there are many technical, logistical and economic challenges such as:

- Choosing a suitable location
- Selecting the appropriate electrolysis method.
- Determining the potential of wind energy based on of the production capacity required to satisfy market demand.
- Storage and transportation.
- Infrastructure and electrical network design.
- Installation, operation and maintenance costs.
- Environmental regulations.
- Cultural changes involved.

References

References

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- [3] SKI, “Offshore-Windenergie.” <https://ski-consult.de/taetigkeitsbereiche/offshore-windenergieanlagen/>.
- [4] Renewables Consulting Group, “Offshore Wind Roadmap for Colombia,” 2022.
- [5] “Global Wind Atlas.” <https://globalwindatlas.info/es/> (accessed Sep. 18, 2023).

Thank you for your
attention!